

Rules for Time Classification

Time 1 - Sedation Injection Period	Time 2 - Euthanasia Injection Period, Pre-TOD	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD
during [sedation]	during [euthanasia solution injection]	right as/after [death occurred]	after [death occurred]
administering/administration [sedation]	administering/administration [euthanasia solution injection]	immediately at/after [death occurred]	dead [patient]
before/close to administering [euthanasia solution injection]	as [euthanasia solution injection]	moment/time of [death]	[death] and then
sedated / falling asleep / point of sedation	while [euthanasia solution injection]	when [death occurred]	until the euthanasia was over
	the moment [of euthanasia solution injection]	as soon as [death occurred]	on a stretcher
	done/finished [euthanasia solution injection]	right as/after [death occurred]	deceased [patient]
	horse go/went down	at [death]	[death] has happened
	before [death]	has just [died]	the remains
	last breath	as [death occurred]	grave
	dying	once [death occurred]	recently [dead]
		time of [death]	the euthanized [patient]
		within seconds of [death]	
		a minute after [death]	

Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type	Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
<p>Once when euthanizing a dog, the Husky housemate stayed outside on the front porch. When I came in the home, he was curled up laying in a chair. Just as I finished administering the medication and confirmed cardiac arrest, the Husky outside let out a loud, single solitary howl. That gave me goosebumps and has stuck with me. I have had countless other, less pronounced instances where the other pets in the home, both cats and dogs, just seem to get very quiet and hushed when the procedure is taking place.</p>				Just as I finished administering the medication and confirmed cardiac arrest			outside
<p>I have seen dogs in the hospital start barking right after death of another patient.</p> <p>Commonly, cats who I have not previously seen or even known were in the house either vocalize or come over to observe and/or investigate.</p>				right after death			dogs in the hospital
<p>I have seen animals do a number of things that made me think they were seeing something. Especially very bonded animals tend to act like this. I think vocalizing is always hard for the owners. I did have one cat that was nice when we arrived, he spooned his brother during the euthanasia and then appeared to follow an invisible butterfly (based on how the cat followed "it") to a window and watched for a minute. The cat then ran back to his brother's body and smelled him and then turned and hissed at me and acted like he was going to attack me and my assistant.</p>					during the euthanasia and then		
<p>I was euthanizing a dog, and a cat was locked up in the next room. As the dog arrested, the cat vocalized, and that was the only time it did during the entire visit.</p>				As the dog arrested			locked up in the next room
<p>"Daughter" pug was pacing, agitated and whining while Mama pug was declining from metastasized neoplasia. She stopped all 3 after mama pug heart stopped.</p>					after mama pug heart stopped		
<p>A handful of times another pet would vocalize at the time of death and we generally found that to be more startling and potentially upsetting. I've seen crying and barking separately.</p>				at the time of death			
<p>A parrot in the room during a home euthanasia clearly said "you'll be ok *Patient name*" while I was injecting the pentobarbital solution. I'm not sure when in that immediate process the patient's heart actually stopped, I can't recall, but with the dosing we use oftentimes patients pass during the injection.</p>			while I was injecting the pentobarbital solution. I'm not sure when in that immediate process the patient's heart actually stopped, I can't recall, but with the dosing we use oftentimes patients pass during the injection				
<p>If they have been whining they usually stop making noise once their friend passes. Usually these things are subtle, but once it was very pronounced (pet was all over the housemate that was departing once he was sedated, nuzzling him, checking on him, etc, then abruptly went and settled down in the far side of the room once he had passed). To me it's very touching, they seem to be at peace and no longer feel a need to protect their friend because they understand they aren't hurting or vulnerable any longer.</p> <p>One time (out of hundreds) I have had a housemate that was friendly with me at first suddenly start growling and bristling when their housemate passed. I left quickly, but I feel he was going to become aggressive toward me had I lingered.</p>				abruptly went and settled down in the far side of the room once he had passed			
<p>Animals in backyard began to bark once patient passed</p>				when their housemate passed once patient passed			in backyard
<p>I work in an ER with an ICU wing and sometimes while performing CPR on a patient other animals in the room vocalize (typically in response to the activity of the code). Sometimes once the code is called they stopped vocalizing.</p>				once the code is called			
<p>Sudden onset of howling in a dog when its mate goes into cardiac arrest. The dog was left in the waiting room with a family friend. The whole family was present for the entire euthanasia process in a separate room. I was checking the chest echoes stethoscopically and expecting a cardiac arrest. Almost for a second, the dog in the waiting room with it began an extremely powerful and moving howl that was almost heartbreaking. His crying" did not stop for almost 10 minutes."</p>				when its mate goes into cardiac arrest			The dog was left in the waiting room
<p>Vocalizing (starting/stopping) during or right after has been noticed and it's unclear how much of that was related to reacting to owner cues/emotions during the appointment.</p>			during or right after has been noticed	during or right after has been noticed			
<p>I euthanized a dog in the owner's vehicle, and two dogs in the neighboring yard started to howl right at the moment I finished administering the euthanasia solution. Probably a coincidence. They are coonhounds who bay whenever they see someone on the sidewalk but the timing was remarkable. I couldn't see the sidewalk from where I was standing so I couldn't say if someone was walking there or not. The deceased dog's owner felt they were honoring his dog, so he appreciated it.</p>			at the moment I finished administering the euthanasia solution				in the neighboring yard
<p>During an at-home euthanasia of a dog (performed in the family's backyard), the owners and their other dog were all sitting nearby when the pet's heart stopped. Their other dog (who had not barked at all before, not at us entering the yard, not at trucks going by) stared at the area around/above the dog who had passed and barked several times.</p>				when the pet's heart stopped			
<p>Vocalizing/stop vocalizing - I have witnessed growling or whining dogs quiet down after a housemate's passing.</p>				immediately after the housemate's passing	after a housemate's passing		
<p>I once saw an energetic, young dog, who was excited with my presence, immediately become very subdued, quiet and outwardly depressed immediately after the housemate's passing. It was palpable and the client recognized it too.</p>				As I gave the injection			
<p>I euthanized 1 dog, while his companion dog slept next to him. As I gave the injection the sleeping dog woke up and began to howl and appeared to watch something rise above his companion...this went on for at least a min.</p>			While administering fatal plus				
<p>While administering fatal plus to nonviable kittens post abortion a cage of kittens started screaming and climbing the cages [after] being quiet and calm all day.</p>				exact moment of cardiac arrest			
<p>A fellow dog in the household was asleep on a bed near where we were euthanizing a different dog. At the exact moment of cardiac arrest, the sleeping dog woke up, sat up and looked around and vocalized.</p>							
<p>Other dogs in other houses barking, crows suddenly stop caring when they had been very loud just moments before.</p>							in other houses

Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type

	Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
I did have one case where another dog started whining because the owner started sobbing at arrest.				at arrest			
I have seen a cat leave her cat friend's side when cardiac arrest occurred to go to the open window to chirp at an empty blue sky for 2-3 minutes.				when cardiac arrest occurred			
Right as the heart stopped all three dogs present began barking and ran towards the door that was open (screen was shut so they could not go any further) Nothing was noted outside that they could have been barking at (we checked) and they all began simultaneously, as opposed to one barking and the others joining in.				Right as the heart stopped			
The birds seem to show up as the pet is transitioning and sing loudly.				as the pet is transitioning			
I've seen a very active Husky settle down and go silent as I started to push the euthanasia solution for his 'sister' - they were in the same room. Alternatively, with another family, I've heard a large dog start howling elsewhere in the house as I started to push the euthanasia drug.			as I started to push the euthanasia solution				elsewhere in the house
Animals that are whining or vocalizing tend to still and settle as their housemate passes.				as their housemate passes			
I have had sounds from other rooms happen at the time of arrest - doors closing, music suddenly stop, other pets stop barking or stop barking at that moment.				at that moment			other rooms
Usually owners are distressed & having other pets vocalize tends to exacerbate their grief & sometimes makes them feel their mates are protesting.							
I often saw companion animals (dogs) became quieter and showing a reluctance to approach the dead pet. [...] They sometimes looked a bit worried/anxious.					the dead pet after the pet passes		
Sometimes after the pet passes the other dog may even seem to "get it" by having a quieter demeanor or change in expression.							
I've seen pets vocalize just before or just as I'm administering euthanasia solution. This happened more earlier in my career, when sometimes that would be the only medication we administered. For many years now, I've sedated & anesthetized pets first, then administered euthanasia solution. It's much less distressing for all involved, the pets, their family, & our staff.	<-- Not included in long-form analysis, because it is referring to the euthanized animal vocalizing						
I really only remember one. But I know it has happened more than once. I was giving a patient with a suspected brain tumor pentobarbital IV and was one of the only times I didn't give a sedative first. During admin the patient began vocalizing	<-- Not included in long-form analysis, because it is referring to the euthanized animal vocalizing						
Animal-Approach / Depart					until the euthanasia was over		
Dog sat at the cat's side until the euthanasia was over, and then walked away and laid down.					after the other pet has passed		
Often times cats will come out after the other pet has passed. Sometimes a cat or dog will move closer to its owner when the other pet has passed					on a stretcher		
"After a euthanasia, we transported the deceased pet on a stretcher to the door. We had to lay the stretcher down to get our shoes on. The other pet followed us and approached and laid down on the deceased pet.			During and after a euthanasia		During and after a euthanasia		
During and after a euthanasia, the other pet snuggles up to the crying/sad owner. "					after their housemate has passed		
Many times I see pets in the same room walk away from the body after their housemate has passed.							
"I saw a cat curl up with the dog and once the heart stop, got up and walked away.					once the heart stop		
I've participated in a few euthanasias where other pets were present and they sometimes approach the body to inspect, then walk away calmly. Owners often find this comforting, a sign the other pet understands and accepts what has happened.					what has happened after passing		
Butterflies landing on body after passing, appearances of birds, caterpillars too.					After the dog passed		
I have also seen several housemates walk away from or up to the animal around the time of passing. In one instance, a kitty was sitting on her doggy friend during the doggy euthanasia. After the dog passed, the kitty got up and walked away.					after arrest		
I have had housemates and even wildlife vocalize or appear after arrest.				at time of death			
I've had housemates appear and disappear at time of death.							
A canine patient had already been sedated (Telazol/Ace/Torb) and we were administering IV euthanasia solution (almost done with full dose). The patient's other dog friend ran up to her. The dog being euthanized appeared to be unconscious but then set up. The dogs touched nose to nose and looked into each other's eyes for a few seconds. Then the dog laid back down and passed.			we were administering IV euthanasia solution (almost done with full dose)				
I've also seen housemates approach the body to sniff around or purposely stay away from the body.							
Euthanizing an elderly dog at a farm. We were sitting by a small garden and garden bench. Myself and my technician along with the owner. About the time we were to start administering the euthanasia solution several barn cats ran over and sat on the bench next to the dog. They stayed sitting silent for about 5 minutes then slowly walked away after dog passed. The dog did not live at the farm only visited a few times many years before and the cats were new to the property. It was very touching.		About the time we were to start administering the euthanasia solution					
If other pets are present most approach. Some seemed "freaked" by it, others sniff and want to just leave.					after dog passed		

Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type

	Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
Often another pet in the home will show a sudden interest in the patient being euthanized or display an unusual behavior just as they pass							
The only experience I've had with another pet reacting a specific way after his brother was euthanised was when he came and laid on his brother's deceased body and refused to be removed, even after 10 minutes.					deceased body		
Many pets will come up and sniff their deceased companion. I have had a couple small dogs start whimpering and pawing at their deceased companion. I have had a couple cats come up and curl up touching beside or laying on top of their deceased dog companion.					deceased companion		
As patient passed a flock of snow geese flew over calling as if they were there to accompany her.				As patient passed			
I've seen dogs no longer respect the personal space of the deceased pet such as stepping on them to get to the client.					deceased pet		
I have also seen companion animals stay at the euthanased animals side until the exact moment that I hear the heartbeat stop, then they leave				exact moment that I hear the heartbeat stop			
Just after the euthanasia of a geriatric pony, his paddock mate came over, sniffed him, and then laid down on his side next to the body. It was a touching moment to everyone present				Just after the euthanasia			
Most typical response from living pets to deceased pet is a quick sniff of the body or maybe just the air around the body. Sometimes they will get up and leave as the animal dies, sometimes shy pets will finally come into the room when pet passes. Once I had a cat hiss and swat at the deceased pet. I had a Rottweiler guard the deceased body and attack the owner when they insisted they move. Rarely but a few times I've had dogs push the deceased pet to try to get them to move/play.				as the animal dies	the deceased		
I have been in a situation when euthanizing a cat, the other cat housemates lined up around the perimeter of the room, as if they were holding vigil but giving space. Once the cat had died, they turned away and left.				Once the cat had died			
I find that dogs are more likely to approach the body and sniff it before turning away, and cats will often retreat from the body without sniffing or otherwise exploring.							
I experienced this during the euthanasia of one of my own cats at home. A colleague conducted the euthanasia. As she pushed the euthanasia solution IV, my other cat, who had been quietly laying on her bed nearby, suddenly leaped up and fled the room. My colleague noted she has witnessed many of these sorts of occurrences and was not surprised at all.			As she pushed the euthanasia solution				
If another pet is in the room they wander past the deceased, sometimes a quick sniff to see why the owners are upset, sometimes no specific reaction, just seem to be seeking the owners' attention.							
I had one patient stay in the room watching her housemate dog from a nearby chair. I gave SQ premeds, and she stayed and watched us. As soon as I started injecting IV pentobarbital, she left the room. She came back into the room once my patient had died.			as I started injecting IV pentobarbital				
I have also seen dogs approach their dead 'siblings' body after death to sniff them.					after death		
Other pets are curious to see the deceased pet. Dogs typically look, then move on to other things that interest them. Cats will sometimes linger.					the deceased pe		
Commonly, cats who I have not previously seen or even known were in the house either vocalize or come over to observe and/or investigate. Many times over my 5 years providing in-home end of life care, families have told me they have a cat who hides and would never usually come out with a stranger in the house, but said cat will appear as their other pet is passing, even if they are still nervous around me specifically.				as their other pet is passing			
I did have one cat that was nice when we arrived, he spooned his brother during the euthanasia and then appeared to follow an invisible butterfly (based on how the cat followed "it") to a window and watched for a minute. The cat then ran back to his brother's body and smelled him and then turned and hissed at me and acted like he was going to attack me and my assistant.					during the euthanasia and then		
A horse was euthanized and was visible from the fence line where others were at pasture. As the horse went down, all of the horses lined the fence. They stood together after the other horse had passed for a few minutes then all walked away at the same time.			As the horse went down		after the other horse had passed for a few minutes then		
It is common for the other dogs to depart from the area while the pet being euthanized is falling asleep from the premedication.		while the pet being euthanized is falling asleep from the premedication					
1) Dogs were barking/running around in back yard the entire appointment and immediately at TOD they come to the back door, silent, and stare in through the glass. 2) Littermate was in yard and ignored me/family entire appointment. Then at TOD approached the dying pet and licked their ear for the duration of the euthasol administration until I witnessed active signs of death (pupil dilation).				immediately at TOD they come to the back door at TOD			
I have had on a few occasions have other pets in the home become aggressive toward me right before administering a lethal injection or stand directly over the body for an extended time.		right before administering a lethal injection					
I had one cat (cat A) hug the other cat (cat B). Cat A curled up next to cat B during the sedation (for about 10 minutes) and euthanasia process. He was also licking cat B's head continuously. Once I pushed the Euthasol and cat B died, cat A stood up right away and left.		during the sedation		Once I pushed the Euthasol and cat B died			
Pets leave or enter the room after the pet is deceased. I distinctly remember looking over at a housemate dog during an IHE and the instant the heart stopped he (otherwise resting with his head on the ground) picked his head up and looked back over his tail to look at his now deceased housemate. That was a few years ago and I can see the day clearly.					after the pet is deceased		
Most companion animals that attend a euthanasia, smell the remains then go to the door to leave.					smell the remains		
Many cats and dogs approach the body close to the administration of the euthanasia agent, and either stare into my eyes or hold space for their housemate.		close to the administration of the euthanasia agent					

Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type

	Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation at the point of heavy sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
Many cats approach the euthanasia at the point of heavy sedation and sniff the patient's body and eventually walk away. Most often, animals approach the body warily, especially if there was an abrupt decline prior to euthanasia. Some sniff, paw at or lay down with the remains.					lay down with the remains		
I have observed 1000's of household pets and their reactions to the remaining housemate who was being euthanized. Their reactions are mainly after the pet passed: acceptance/ignoring the pet once they realize they've passed (ie don't look at the face), turn and walk away quietly or attempt to comfort the owner.					after the pet passed		
I've had horses go down from euthanasia and most other horses nearby will whinny, take off running, or come near the body and sniff them. Some have tried pawing at them. One horse tried nursing off the mare (it was the adult horse's mom).			horses go down from euthanasia				
I was at a euthanasia where there were two other dogs present and after euthanizing the patient and putting them in a basket, one of the other dogs walked over and laid her head on top of the body and basket and did not want to move. The parents had never seen her do anything like this before and even mentioned they didn't feel like these two dogs were particularly "close"					after euthanizing the patient and putting them in a basket		
Herd mates can and appeared to smell the body and then moved away.							
I have often found a companion to move closer or away from a deceased pet at the time of death. They are often very quiet and settled during the euthanasia procedure.				at the time of death			
Most commonly, an owner would remark that a shy housemate cat was observing and then approaching, striking them as odd or unusual behavior for that pet.							
A flock of crow swoop over then fly away another even crow that landed in a tree above us and watched then flew away when the dog passed, I have seen butterflies land on deceased pets.				when the dog passed			
Almost every single time there is a bonded, interested housemate present they may be approaching their sick friend or guarding their sick friend even when they are conscious and still later when they are fully sedated (not conscious), but almost always they will settle down and walk away and sit on the other side of the room and usually put their head down on the ground and rests as soon as the housemate has passed. On many occasions this happens just before the heart stops beating, it's very predictable for me. I've only not seen that happen if the housemate observing is not visible to me. If they have been whining they usually stop making noise once their friend passes. Usually these things are subtle, but once it was very pronounced (pet was all over the housemate that was departing once he was sedated, nuzzling him, checking on him, etc, then abruptly went and settled down in the far side of the room once he had passed).		when they are fully sedated	just before the heart stops beating	abruptly went and settled down in the far side of the room once he had passed			
I am a mobile in-home euthanasia veterinarian so I perform euthanasias a lot more frequently and interact with members of the household more closely than in a clinic. Most of the times, owners will allow their other pets in the household to sniff "goodbye" after death. I have seen housemate dogs approach the sedated pet during procedures and lay next to them, sniff them, etc. I have also had housemate dogs bark/become slightly aggressive toward to me as if they know what I am there for. Some dogs are very anxious and will cry/whine while their housemate is being euthanized. Housemate dogs tend to react more to euthanasia than housemate cats. cats tend to hide or be more curious of my equipment if anything, and will usually not approach the body on their own. I do hear of owners saying in the weeks/days leading up to the euthanasia appointment, that the housemates will often treat the pet differently as if they know their friend is dying (i.e staying away/giving the pet space, cuddling with the pet, sniffing the pet, etc.).							
Fun story: I went to the home of one of my former clients from GP to euthanize her rat terrier [animal's name] who had been battling kidney failure for a long time. We performed the euthanasia in the owner's backyard and it was a sunny spring day. Right after I pushed the Euthasol and [animal's name] took her last breath, a dragonfly flew by and landed on her body. It was a very sweet moment and I truly believe it was [animal's name] taking residence in her next life!		the sedated pet	after I pushed the Euthasol and [animal's name] took her last breath				
The owner wanted the dog to inspect and be close to the deceased pet. The dog wanted nothing to do with the deceased and moved across the room to her bed.					the deceased pet		
People will occasionally bring housemate dogs for euthanasias. The housemates typically move away from the patient at time of death. When we had our own dog euthanized at home, our other dog refused to be in the room the entire time				at time of death			
The other surprising action I noticed was another animal in the family approaching the recently deceased pet and licking their face/ear almost immediately after they were deceased.					recently deceased pet after the procedure was complete		
It was an at-home euthanasia of a dog. There was a cat on the couch in the room, who left after the procedure was complete.					deceased patient		
On one in home euthanasia another dog in the family came up and sniffed the deceased patient and then vomited.							
The owners want the pet to see dead patient the dog came over but then turned and walked away. More like nothing left to see then seeing something. Actually, completely ignoring the dead patient is my most common experience.					dead patient		
I can recall a few instances of other pets walking away although mainly the animals make peace with the pet before or after the procedure, not typically during.							
Clinic cat consistently stands outside rooms during/after euthanasia (never others) and will often sit quietly with the body afterwards.			during/after		during/after		
Typically, the animals were encouraged by their owners to approach the body, as a form of closure.							
I encourage the handlers to allow the horse's companion to approach their deceased pasture mate... Most of the time, the companion horse will come sniff the deceased horse, maybe nibble/lick, then go back to grazing.					Deceased		
I euthanized one of my longtime pets (dog), and allowed a companion dog to view the body after death. She sniffed him and then walked away, like she knew he was gone.					after death		
Robin birds usually seen							
Come to/depart from body - I have witnessed this many times. Usually it is a housemate leaving the deceased body. Others have come to sniff afterwards. Cats seem more keen on snuggling with a sick housemate then leaving after they have passed.					after they have passed		

Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type

	Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
When euthanizing a horse the rest of the herd came up and formed a circle around us. Once the horse had passed one mare led them up. After smelling and nuzzling the deceased mare who was the alpha of the group, the mare that had led them up whinnied and led the herd off				Once the horse had passed	the deceased		
Animals approach and depart the deceased, but there aren't usually other animals in the room for a euthanasia.							
Not much more than the animals approaching, sniffing, and walking away.							
Have certainly seen animals who were present come up to the body more than back away.							
I don't often have clients that bring housemates in for euthanasia of the other animal in the home since I'm in a veterinary clinic but during the few times I've had about half the housemates make some sign they knew their "friend" was passing by moving closer to them during that moment or moving away right after they had passed.							
Most dogs approach the dead; cats, if allowed in the room (I've had too many knock out catheters), tend to back away initially.							
A couple of dogs brought favored toys to the deceased. One young cat tapped on her old dog friend's head for a few minutes; it was how she used to wake him. There were no dry eyes as she gradually slowed then stopped the tapping.							
Clinic cat snuggles up with deceased animal.					deceased animal		
I have seen one pet come up to the deceased as cardiac arrest occurred and one animal leave the space. The owners were primarily focused on the deceased pet but did notice the one animal leaving and wondered out loud if they knew.				as cardiac arrest occurred			
Crows suddenly appearing when they hadn't been there before.							
Many times witnessing housemate animals respond in some way—being very nervous or anxious, but settling down as the patient is dying, refusing to acknowledge the body after death, turning in the room to face the opposite direction.							
The most memorable moment was when a companion dog snuggled up next to his dying buddy while my eyes were closed, listening to the patient's heartbeat right as the patient passed.			dying buddy				
Livestock are typically quite nosy and will approach the remains, or just try to enter the barn while we're doing euthanasia."					approach the remains		
I had a farm pet that had a sudden end of his life. When the farm cats left his body we knew he had succumbed to his trauma and was no longer in pain.							
I have seen a cat leave her cat friends side when cardiac arrest occurred to go to the open window to chirp at an empty blue sky for 2-3 minutes... Animals that have not been seen the entire appointment suddenly appear when cardiac arrest occurs. Animals that were present for the entire process, get up to leave at the moment of cardiac arrest.				when cardiac arrest occurred			
Cats abruptly run off and leave the time of cardiac arrest. Cats that have been cuddled with their sibling my patient, get up and quietly leave.				time of cardiac arrest			
It is very common when euthanizing an elder of the herd for all the horses loose in the field to stop, line up and face us and be very still as the euthanasia is performed. I've had horses lay down next to a euthanized horse and sleep next to or guard grave sites for long times (days to weeks) after.					grave sites		
I and families have seen and heard cardinals right outside the window during the dying process. I've had cats come in and sit on or next to the deceased. The cats almost always come in out of nowhere and are always calm. Some of the owners have said that in life, the cat did not interact with the now deceased but then they waltzed in and sat on the body or the stretcher. Some came in and sat next to me for the final injection. I've had other dogs come and lay down next to the deceased. I've also had many walk over and then leave. The birds seem to show up as the pet is transitioning and sing loudly.			during the dying process		next to the deceased		
I have had other pets who were pacing or standing suddenly sit when I'm done giving euthanasia meds. I have had cats come in when pet was sedated, left when I was giving euthanasia meds and then returned to smell deceased.		when pet was sedated	when I'm done giving euthanasia meds		smell deceased		
I've seen wildlife appear many times at the moment they are passing. I've seen kitties approach and hiss and run away.				at the moment they are passing			
Fairly often at homes the other pets in the home will either move away right after or will come close to be near the family members right after.				right after			
Only when euthanizing my own pets, the rest of the animal family mills about. They all take turns rotating in to check out the recently passed family member.					recently passed		
I started out in equine/large animal practice (while simultaneously doing at-home small animal euthanasias), then switched to small animal. There was much more concern among herd mates with large animal euthanasias than I ever experience in small animals. I saw horses lick the eyeballs of their dead friend, try to lift them by their manes, and cows especially were very concerned about their dead pasture mate. As for dogs, I always tried to give my own and others' dogs the same chance to understand their friend was dead...and they didn't care. They were always more interested in the people. I always found that dogs didn't seem to notice there was a change for several days. I've done hundreds of euthanasias at this point, likely amongst both large and small animals unfortunately.					dead pasture mate		
Butterfly flying by the cat's body							
Clients that bring another pet to the euthanasia felt sad that the other pet wanted to get away from the euthanized pet. This has also happened at home euthanasias. My dog didn't want his euthanized best friend to be separated from him. He followed the doctor carrying her to the car for me. He looked for her for weeks.					the euthanized pet		
When doing at home euthanasia, sometimes if another pet is allowed in the room they may walk toward the deceased animal to smell and be nearby.					deceased animal		
1) A hound whose owner shared he wished the wild turkeys would have come back as the dog loved to bark at them from the living room window. He shared the coyotes had gotten bad and they hadn't seen turkeys in three years. Within seconds of cardiac arrest we could hear a tapping sound (me the pet owner and a vet that was with me that day). When we looked up there were 3 turkeys standing on the front porch looking in at us in the living room, pecking on the glass!!				Within seconds of cardiac arrest			
On more than one occasion the other pet from the household was present and either left the side of the deceased or approached them as cardiac arrest occurred. I can not assign any specific cause for the reaction.				as cardiac arrest occurred			

	Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type	Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
	In my experience especially in large animals where it is more likely that other animals are around while performing euthanasia, it's very common that others will approach the body and sniff it for a few minutes before going back to their activities. Donkeys can spend a considerable amount of time doing this. Dogs do this too.							
	If the pet parent has had the difficult conversation with their pet before the euthanasia procedure, most animals leave the sick, or useless, body quickly. I've only given a small amount of the full dose of anesthesia. I've felt their energy leave the room.							
Child-Stare	I have seen young children getting up to go to the open window, or if to small to walk, look at the open window and wave goodbye. I've experienced several instances where either an animal or small child looks up and away. One child said out loud, "there he goes" and pointed up. Young children looking up felt kind of creepy? While I've had 2-5 instances of children staring up into the air I think all of those instances were children simply unsure of what to do in the specific situation. For many children I suspect it's their first experience with death and possibly seeing their parent/guardian grieve. Averting their gaze is probably a coping mechanism to disassociate from the event entirely.						I have seen young children getting up to go to the open window, or if to small to walk, look at the open window and wave goodbye.	
	I believe that children are pure souls and see things that most adults can not see unless they are believers and my own experiences through my childhood and adulthood makes me a believer.	<-- Not included in long-form analysis, because it does not describe an event						
Child-Point	I have seen young children getting up to go to the open window, or if to small to walk, look at the open window and wave goodbye. I've experienced several instances where either an animal or small child looks up and away. One child said out loud, "there he goes" and pointed up.						I have seen young children getting up to go to the open window, or if to small to walk, look at the open window and wave goodbye.	
Temperature	I really wondered about myself. I get extremely hot towards the end of the administration of the euthanasia solution. My ears & head feel like they are on fire. I have done home euthanasia, clinic euthanasia & farm call equine euthanasia. Hair standing on end, goosebumps in hot weather After I had removed the patients body and the room was empty I could feel genuine heat / warmth as I wiped down the bench I have occasionally noticed the room can feel darker or colder after euthanasias. There's a chill that I always just associated with the nerves of the situation, typically very highly emotional environment, but occasionally while performing the euthanasia without loved ones present. I have been known to feel a chill not temperature related after a passing.			towards the end of the administration of the euthanasia solution			After I had removed the patients body after euthanasia after a passing	
	I have actually never thought about it until now. I have been a vet for 18 years [...]. I assumed the temperature change was physiologic from me or the owner being stressed etc. But the client and I were suddenly freezing before death was confirmed by auscultation but after the pet stopped breathing with the injection of pentobarbital.			before death was confirmed by auscultation but after the pet stopped breathing with the injection of pentobarbital				
	Significant instances in my career that I cannot explain [...]. temperature change i think, cannot really place it. It was a home euthanasia of a dog, family, music blaring, sad, sad event. dog at window on bed, after injecting the dog with solution, which went perfect, i felt something behind me?? cold draft? I turned, nothing. No one else was reacting as they were engaged in the dog. I have been part of euthanasia in shelters more than in the veterinary clinic. I have experienced more temperature drops in the shelter. No other animals or family present.			after injecting the dog with solution				
	I had a mobile practice early in my career. I did many home euthanasias. More than once I felt an energy or temperature change at the time of euthanasia. I just felt a kind of low body temperature and surrounding right after for just a few seconds. This happened twice I guess. Times where there has been distinct temperature &/or energy shifts.				at the time of euthanasia right after			
	The most memorable euthanasia was a dog who was surrounded by his entire family and his canine sister. She was laying by him in a bed, turned away from him. The family was sitting on a sofa and chairs around the dog. A cat was present. This particular family believed all their animals should be present for the experience so they could understand what was happening. I first met this family and their animals three days prior when we diagnosed end of life disease. Before the euthanasia the canine sister seemed a little anxious, was making small movements. During the procedure, the family was silent and the sister canine became more settled. The cat came to watch on the sofa with the family. The same moment we told the owners he had passed, the sister canine relaxed her entire body and exhaled. It felt like pressure was released from the room. The temperature changed and it was very positive. The cat left the area. We said our goodbyes. The sister canine didn't leave her brother who had passed. When the doctor and I were in the van getting ready to leave, we shared our experience. I have not forgotten it since then.				moment we told the owners he had passed			

Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type

		Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
Wind	Right after the passing of a geriatric black lab, the owners mentioned they were going to open a window because it was an old Victorian tradition to allow a spirit to pass. But before they could do that the back door flew open- it was a nice calm day. We just laughed and said she wanted to go out the back door.				Right after the passing		back door flew open	
	The most remarkable experience I have had was in an elderly atopic dog with deep yeast dermatitis and alopecia. It was miserable. Just as I finished pushing the IV pentobarbital, the dog shook like it just got out of a pool and all of us present felt a gust of wind, the curtains on the nearest window trembled and then there was silence. We all gasped and got goose bump[s]. It was [as] if the dog shook off its body and ran out the window in a burst of joy.				Just as I finished pushing the IV pentobarbital		curtains on the nearest window trembled	
	In one case a door slammed upstairs about a minute after the death, with items knocked over on a bureau under the window in the direction of the window (the opposite way I would have expected if wind blew in the window)					a minute after the death	items knocked over on a bureau under the window in the direction of the window	
	The owners of the chihuahua we euthanized said she had always been the dog that flew into rooms like a bat outta hell. When she passed, the shutters blew open and a gush of wind came in. We all were taken back and laughed joyfully.					When she passed	shutters blew open	
	When the patient passed, there was the back door, it was like a sliding door, that swung open...it was dramatic... It was very comforting for the family (interview)					When the patient passed	back door, it was like a sliding door, that swung open (interview)	
	A fire that was out 14hrs prior popped loudly and began burning again at the moment of cardiac arrest (family had phones out claiming they witnessed a Miracle).					at the moment of cardiac arrest		
	I was in an enclosed bedroom, no windows or doors open, and at the time of death the wind chime that was above the bed started chiming.					at the time of death		
	The most common thing I have witnessed is either an unexplained breeze or gusts of wind							
	We were euthanizing a very aggressive dog and felt a draft of air at the time of death.					at the time of death		
	I have had sounds from other rooms happen at the time of arrest - doors closing, music suddenly stop, other pets stop barking at that moment					at the time of arrest as a patient died	doors closing	
	Once I did feel a whoosh of air towards me as a patient died. I often sense that they have passed.					at time of death		
	Chimes sounding at time of death when there was no wind, even a chime inside a home.					as the pet passed away		
	The most memorable experience was a pet that was euthanized but [there was] a surviving spouse. The windchime that was a memorial for the deceased spouse (and primary owner of the pet) chimed without any other wind as the pet passed away.						after patient passed	
	Chimes blowing after patient passed.							
	Doors open randomly, candle going out once.							Doors open randomly
	Once a door dramatically blew open at time of death					at time of death		door dramatically blew open
	I have felt a breeze on several occasions.							
	Wind chimes moving on quiet wind days at the moment of cardiac arrest.					at the moment of cardiac arrest		
	The positive experience with the fire whoosing up was from curiosity of timing. Did it mean something?							
	Electronics	Electronics, tv turning off on its own, light flickering.						
TV in different room turned on								
I have witnessed many 1000s euthanasias. I have also felt in the rare pet an energy/current pass through me or give me goose bumps as the pet dies. The electrical malfunction was an odd one. Service dog to a veteran. Moment it died, all the alarms went off in the house, the tv turned on, the answering machine clicked on.						Moment it died		
When the patient went into cardiac arrest the lights either flickered a second or shut completely off						When the patient went into cardiac arrest		
Although I have never seen anything other than electrical activity I have seen that occur more often than it being a coincidence. Nothing more than a flicker meaning I haven't seen a clock stop of a light turn off or on completely but there has definitely been a electrical activity.								
Once the lights flickered right as the pet passed.						right as the pet passed		
I have seen lights flicker right after a euthanasia.						right after a euthanasia		
On only one occasion, a song came one over the telephone speaker in an exam room.								
Electricity going between people. Hair standing on end, goosebumps in hot weather								
experienced car alarms, cell phones, songs, electronics go on right after death.						right after death		
On many occasions my radio will play in my vehicle as I leave with the deceased, even though I never turn it on when I work and it never turns itself on after non-euthanasia appointments.						as I leave with the deceased		
One time we were in the living room and the TV equipment very clearly had power issues at the time of death. Nobody was able to make sense of it but I don't think it necessarily has a positive or negative impact on any of us.					at the time of death			
The lights flickered a few times & the owner said it was another dog calling to the deceased one						the deceased one		
After home euthanasia, I got in my car and dash lights that had been out for a few months came back on. Then were out again the next day.						After home euthanasia		
songs stopping or skipping.								
once something started playing music at time of death					at time of death			

Long-Form PMO Descriptions Organized by PMO-Type		Exclusion Notes	Time 1 - Sedation	Time 2 - Euthanasia	Time 3 - TOD	Time 4 - After TOD	Architectural Apertures	Isolated Animals Vocalizing
	I have had sounds from other rooms happen at the time of arrest - doors closing, music suddenly stop, other pets stop barking or stop barking at that moment.				at the time of arrest			
	Our euthanasia room constantly has issues with the computer malfunctioning, the mouse will move on it own							
Light	At home, outside euthanasia 6 people present, body placed in grave 2 of 6 people noticed an "orb" moving from grave to the sky. I observed them both have a reaction and noticed at the same time.					body placed in grave		
	Often light will shine upon the pet that exact moment it passes.							
Mist Formation	N/A							
Wavy Distortion	N/A							